

POSSIBILITIES OF USING INTERACTIVE SHOOTING TRAINERS IN TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF SHOOTING TRAINING TO CADETS OF THE ARMED FORCES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article scientifically analyzes the possibilities of using interactive shooting simulators in training the cadets of the Academy of Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: shooting training, interactive shooting range, modular training technology.

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The right of a serviceman of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan to use a firearm is provided for in the relevant legal documents, and in this regard, shooting training is one of the leading educational subjects for cadets of the Higher Military Educational Institutions of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and in the future, it is aimed at effectively solving their service and professional tasks by military personnel.

Effectiveness in learning this science can be achieved only in conditions of regular practical training.

Ability to use electronic technical equipment and simulators to train readiness to fire, quickly prepare the weapon for combat and the technique of firing the first shot, correct grip and aim, regular practice of shooting, shooting without a bullet.

The use of modern interactive laser shooting ranges serves to increase the level of formation of professional skills of students related to the use of firearms, to save resources and funds, and to increase the quality and efficiency of firearms training. Electronic shooting simulators should be classified as "didactic equipment" that allows not only to simulate the process of live shooting, but also to bring the situation of using weapons as close as possible to the future professional activities of military personnel.

At the Armed Forces Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the technical capabilities of interactive laser beams are widely used in shooting training exercises. Laser simulators allow you to perform all the main actions of shooting training: working in pairs, supporting partners and fighting to the last shot, quickly removing the weapon from the storage and putting it into a combat position,

aiming and pressing the trigger. It is important for the learner to have the opportunity to independently control his actions and efficiency, analyze his mistakes, while providing the possibility of the teacher's intervention at any stage of the exercise. The use of interactive simulators makes shooting training visual and interesting, and significantly increases the motivation of students.

Video projection equipment of electronic gunners allows creating images of targets on the screen in certain situations. The user sets the target characteristics of targets. In addition to the static behavior of targets, it is also possible to adjust their movement parameters: target rotation (from front to side, in random order), target drop (after hitting the target, it drops from vertical to horizontal), target lift (raising the target from horizontal to vertical position). The cadet fires a laser gun; the monoblock camera receives the laser point and transmits relevant data to the computer to evaluate the effectiveness of the shot.

The software allows you to perform speed and accuracy analysis and print out the results not only for each shot, but also for a collection of shots. The video plot constructor allows you to simulate scenarios of tactical actions using firearms, which helps students to perform exercises of various levels of complexity in individual and group exercises that maximally simulate real conditions for solving professional situations.

The use of interactive simulators in shooting training of cadets of the Armed Forces Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is organized step by step on the basis of modular technology. The team of the department has developed special exercises in order to increase the effectiveness of training of cadets in shooting training[4].

The advantages of the interactive shooting range are the wide range of opportunities for modeling situations, the presence of changing situations, the position of the target and its distance to it. Pedagogical experience shows that the results of shooting in simulators usually produce better indicators than the results of similar exercises on the range. This can be explained by the absence of fear associated with shooting and minimizing the psychological factors of negative impact.

The use of interactive simulators allows you to develop shooting skills in accordance with shooting techniques without using ammunition. The use of electronic shooting devices and devices in the early stages of training allows you to quickly master the technique of correct aiming, adjusting the breath and optimizing the trigger. The results of modern research show that using the capabilities of an interactive laser shooting range almost doubles the effectiveness of high-speed selective fire training on emerging targets[2], reduces fear and learning to shoot and minimizes errors in trigger pull[1], increases the quality of cadets' shooting

readiness[5]. Despite the fact that the indicators of performance in short-range interactive firing live are significantly higher compared to firing at a long distance from the target, the latter corresponds better to the results of control exercises carried out on the test site at ranges[3].

The preliminary results of the use of technical equipment and simulators in training the cadets of the Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan in shooting ability allow us to draw the following conclusions:

Training with the use of interactive shooting range on the eve of shooting exercises helps trainees to successfully master the conditions, techniques and rules of shooting, which subsequently leads to an increase in the effectiveness of exercises during shooting. will come;

the use of interactive simulators ensures the creation of conditions for the use of firearms as close as possible to real situations of professional activity;

Undoubtedly, the capabilities of interactive simulators are significantly higher than the capabilities of tools and equipment traditionally used by cadets in shooting training. cannot replace.

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